

Detached-Eddy Simulation of Normal Flow past Flat Plates: The Influence from Corner Curvature

Jacob Andersen¹ and Claes Eskilsson¹

¹ Department of the Built Environment, Aalborg University
Aalborg, Denmark

ABSTRACT

Normal flow past flat plates at high Reynolds numbers is applied in various engineering contexts. To accurately model such flows for slender plates in Computational Fluid Dynamics requires scale-resolving rather than scale-modelling methods. The present paper uses Detached-Eddy Simulation to investigate the influence of plate corner curvature on global flow quantities such as the time-averaged drag coefficient. The effect of corner curvature is mapped and collated with the literature. Solution verification is carried out to quantify the numerical uncertainty. The time-averaged drag coefficient increases significantly between semi-cylindrically rounded ($\langle C_D \rangle_t = 2.28$) and sharp-cornered ($\langle C_D \rangle_t = 2.42$) plates.

KEY WORDS: drag coefficient, flat plate, CFD, scale-resolving simulations; DES.

INTRODUCTION

Normal flow past flat plates is a canonical research topic within fluid dynamics with seminal works of, e.g., Fage and Johansen (1927) and Fail et al. (1959). The topic remains relevant to modern engineering due to its complexity and vast application range. Flat plates in normal flows are thus seen in engineering applications such as interceptors on high-speed crafts, energy collectors of oscillating surging type wave energy converters, and heave plates on offshore floating substructures for, e.g., wind turbine generators or solar PV. At practical Reynolds numbers Re (say, $>1e5$), see Eq. 1, the drag is governed by the turbulent wake generated from the flow separation and shedding of large eddies at the plate edges. The normal flow past flat plates is dominated by pressure (form) drag, and for plate thicknesses approaching zero the contribution from skin friction will equal zero. For sharp-cornered plates, the separation points are fixed and the Re -dependency on the drag coefficient C_D , see Eq. 2, is very weak for $Re > 1e3$ (Hoerner, 1965). The influence of the aspect ratio (width to height) was studied in Fail et al. (1957) for flow past flat plates with aspect ratios ranging from one

(square) to 20. The classic work of Fage and Johansen (1927) considered the normal flow at $Re = 1.5e5$ past a flat plate of so-called infinite span or aspect ratio – referring to a physical test setup where flow over the spanwise edges was restricted by wind tunnel walls. The tested plate was therefore nominally two-dimensional, which is an assumption often adopted in both physical and numerical tests of flow past high aspect ratio, i.e., slender, plates. Despite a nominally two-dimensional geometry, the problem remains three-dimensional due to the inherent three-dimensionality of turbulence.

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is widely used in the field of fluid mechanics where it allows for the extraction of virtually any flow variable of interest without affecting the flow; has a highly controllable test setup/environment; and generally, poses a cost-effective alternative to physical tests. CFD from Scale-Modelling Simulation (SMS) techniques in the form of Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) models coupled with Boussinesq-viscosity (industry standard) turbulence models have proven unreliable in large curvature flows past nominally two-dimensional (slender) geometries (Squires et al., 2001, Vatsa et al., 2003, Wu et al., 2022, Shur et al., 2005, Mannini, 2015). Thus, for example Shur et al. (2005) reported how URANS simulations of the high- Re flow past a NACA 0012 airfoil at 90° angle of attack depended considerably on the turbulence model, spanwise dimension, and initial conditions. Only SMS started from the solution from a Scale-Resolving Simulation (SRS) was able to consistently sustain three-dimensionality, and these simulations still significantly overpredicted the time-averaged drag coefficient relative to physical tests and SRS – indicating the increased accuracy of SRS relative to SMS in such flow types. SRS with Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) resolves large energetic scales, which tends to be dependent on geometry, boundary conditions, etc., and models small scales, which tends to be more universal and homogeneous. LES resolves scales accounting for about 80% or more of the local turbulence kinetic energy, k , as suggested by Pope (2004). Thus, LES requires high resolutions in time and space – especially within boundary layers where small scales govern – making LES computational costly. This is partially circumvented by the Detached-Eddy Simulation (DES) approach due to Spalart et al. (1997). DES is a hybrid-URANS-LES method which switches from scale-modelling (URANS) to scale-resolving (LES) between attached and detached flow regions. The idea from LES of resolving only the large energetic scales and modelling the small scales is thus further exploited in DES in the sense scale-modelling is used to account for k in attached boundary layers where the accuracy of turbulence models is often high (Durbin, 2021). The present paper focuses on the application of DES to simulate the case of normal flow past a nominally two-dimensional flat plate. The adopted global flow values of interest are the time-averaged drag coefficient $\langle C_D \rangle_t$, the relative recirculation length L_C , and the Strouhal number S_t ; refer to the succeeding section for the definitions applied in the present paper.

LES of the normal flow past flat plates at $Re = 1.5e5$ (as that of Fage and Johansen, 1927) was carried out in the works of Tian et al. (2014) and Díaz-Ojeda et al. (2019). Both works utilized cyclic spanwise boundaries to represent nominally two-dimensional plate geometries and had identical domain sizes as well as plate thicknesses (normalized with the plate height h). In Tian et al. (2014) the relative corner curvature r/h was varied between 0.5% and 1.0% (corresponding to r/t ratios of 25% and 50%, respectively), whereas sharp corners ($r = 0$) were applied in Díaz-Ojeda et al. (2019), see Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Notion for plate geometry as seen from the spanwise plane.

The physical tests in Fage and Johansen (1927) were carried out on a steel plate with a flat front and a rear weakly tapering from the center ($t/h = 0.03$) towards the sharp edges ($t/h \approx 0$). The blockage ratio h/h_c , where h_c is the height of the wind tunnel, was varied between 0.024-0.095. In Hemmati et al. (2018), DNS and LES were carried out for the normal flow past zero-thickness plates (so-called baffles) at moderate $Re = 1.2e3$, thus just inside the range of Re where the global flow values are practically Re -independent according to Hoerner (1987) and Hemmati et al. (2018). All considered numerical test setups have applied either slip, symmetry, or freestream boundary conditions at the chordwise boundaries, which are assessed to have similar blockage effects assuming constant blockage ratio. The environmental load standard DNVGL-RP-C205 (DNV, 2017) presents the time-averaged drag coefficients of rectangular cylinders (rather than flat plates) of $t/h \geq 0.5$ as function of r/h . Information on h/h_c , L_C , and S_t are not given in the DNV standard.

The reviewed literature is summarized in Table 1, where abbreviated reference names are introduced for brevity in figure legends. The influence of corner curvature, by r/h , on the time-averaged drag coefficient is mapped in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Corner curvature versus time-averaged drag coefficient from selected literature, see Table 1. $r/h = 1\%$ corresponds to semi-cylindrical edges for plates of $t/h = 2\%$.

For $Re > 1e3$, flow separation occurs at the upstream corners irrespective of t/h . In the case of flat plates (say, $t/h \lesssim 5\%$), the separated shear layers do not interact with the downstream part of the plate, whereas for higher t/h ratios they do (Mannini, 2015). The curvature of the separated shear layers at the near-wake region increases with t/h until $t/h \approx 0.6$ (Nakaguchi et al., 1968) which poses a global maximum of $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ in the range 0.1-4 (Nakaguchi et al., 1968; Norberg, 1993; Sohankar, 2008). Accordingly, the tests reported in DNV (2017; $t/h = 0.5$) had increased shear layer curvature relative to those of flat plates causing a lower base pressure and consequently larger drag coefficients. That being said, the trend of $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ with r/h in DNV (2017) remains of interest in understanding the same trend in flow past flat plates since the upstream face is identical for constant r/h regardless of t/h , and it is the upstream face which governs the immediate curvature of the separated shear layers (Nakaguchi et al., 1968). The question then remains if the wake-structure interactions at $t/h = 0.5$ drive the correlation of $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ and r/h or if a similar correlation exists for $t/h \ll 1$.

The small geometrical variation of $r/h = 1.0\%$ to 0.5% (from a global geometry point of view) in Tian et al. (2014) influenced the flow noteworthy and resulted in alterations of the global flow values of $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ and L_c , see Table 1 and Fig. 1, whereas S_t remained constant. Multiple studies investigating the case of normal flow past flat plates with sharp corners has been reviewed. By the collation of these studies, the tendency on $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ and L_c with r/h is inconclusive due to the large spread on $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ and L_c at $r/h = 0$. The collated results include not just the parameter variation of r/h , but also multiple others as h/h_c , Re , turbulence inflow intensity, test methodology errors, etc., which compromises an accurate disclosure of the influence of corner curvature.

The aim of the present paper is to map the influence of corner curvature on global flow quantities $\langle C_D \rangle_t$, S_t , and L_c of the flow past nominally two-dimensional flat plates with $r/h \in [0.0, 0.5, 1.0]\%$, where the limits correspond to sharp corners and semicylindrical edges for $t/h = 2\%$. In this, DES is carried out, and solution verification based on the Grid-Convergence Index (GCI) as per Roache (1998) as well as comparison to comparable test setups from LES, DNS and physical experiments are made.

GLOBAL FLOW VALUES

The Reynolds number is calculated from

$$Re = \frac{u_0 h}{\nu}, \quad (1)$$

where h is a characteristic length which for nominal two-dimensional plates simplifies to the plate height, u_0 is the normal freestream velocity, and ν is the kinematic viscosity.

The considered global flow values in the present paper include the time-averaged drag coefficient $\langle C_D \rangle_t$, the relative recirculation length L_c , and the Strouhal number S_t . Throughout the paper the operators $\langle \phi \rangle_t$ and $\langle \phi \rangle_z$ denotes time- and spanwise averaging, respectively, upon the field ϕ . The definitions of the drag coefficient C_D , the relative recirculation length L_c , and the Strouhal number S_t are given in Eqs. 2-4.

Table 1: Summary of the present literature on normal flow past flat plates. *Smag* refers to the Smagorinsky subgrid model.

Reference	Legend	Type	r/h [%]	t/h [%]	h/h _c [-]	$\langle C_D \rangle_t$ [-]	Re [-]	$\langle L_C \rangle_t$ [-]	S _t [-]
Tian et al. (2014)	TIAN	LES Smag	1	2	0.0625	2.20	1.5e5	2.28	0.155
Tian et al. (2014)	TIAN	LES Smag	0.5	2	0.0625	2.30	1.5e5	2.13	0.155
Díaz-Ojeda et al. (2019)	DIAZ	LES Smag	0	2	0.0625	2.34	1.5e5	2.4	0.166
Díaz-Ojeda et al. (2019)	DIAZ	LES WALE	0	2	0.0625	2.20	1.5e5	-	-
Fage and Johansen (1927)	FAGE	Physical	0	0-3	0.0714	2.13	1.5e5	-	0.146
Fage and Johansen (1927)	FAGE	Physical	0	0-3	0.0476	2.05	1.5e5	-	-
Hemmati et al. (2018)	HEMM	LES Smag	0	0	0.0625	2.13	1.2e3	2.51	0.158
Hemmati et al. (2018)	HEMM	DNS	0	0	0.0625	2.13	1.2e3	2.65	0.158
DNV (2017)	DNV	Physical	0	50	-	2.5	1e5	-	-
DNV (2017)	DNV	Physical	2.1	50	-	2.2	1e5	-	-
DNV (2017)	DNV	Physical	8.3	50	-	1.9	1e5	-	-

$$C_D = \frac{F_{drag}}{2\rho Au_0^2}, \quad (2)$$

where F_{drag} is the total drag force, ρ is the fluid density, and A is the frontal area of the plate.

$$L_C = \frac{L}{h}, \quad (3)$$

in which L is the length of the recirculation bubble as found from the time- and spanwise averaged streamwise velocity field.

$$S_t = \frac{f_p h}{u_0}, \quad (4)$$

where f_p is the peak frequency of the lift spectrum (representing the dominating vortex shedding frequency).

NUMERICAL METHOD

As outlined in the introduction, DES is a hybrid-URANS-LES method. The basis of both URANS and LES is the Navier-Stokes equations which express the conservation of mass and momentum for Newtonian fluids. Under the assumptions of incompressibility (constant density) and constant viscosity, the Navier-Stokes equations read

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \cdot U &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} U + \nabla \cdot (UU) &= \nu \nabla^2 U - \frac{\nabla p}{\rho} + g ,\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

where U is the fluid velocity vector, p is pressure, g is the gravitational acceleration vector, and ∇ is the nabla operator.

Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes Equations

The URANS equations exploit the concept of Reynolds-decomposition where flow variables are decomposed into a mean part (e.g., the ensemble average) and a fluctuation part. For a flow variable ϕ this can be expressed as

$$\phi(P, t) = \bar{\phi}(P, t) + \phi'(P, t) , \quad (6)$$

where P is a position vector to any point within a domain, $\bar{\phi}$ denotes the ensemble average of ϕ , and ϕ' denotes the fluctuation of ϕ . The ensemble average of fluctuations then satisfies $\overline{\phi'} = 0$. Reynolds-decomposition and ensemble averaging of Eq. 5 then yields the URANS equations:

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \cdot \bar{U} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \bar{U} + \nabla \cdot (\bar{U}\bar{U}) &= \nu \nabla^2 \bar{U} - \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla \bar{p} + g - \nabla \cdot (\overline{U'U'}) ,\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

which introduces the Reynolds-stress tensor

$$\bar{\sigma}_t = \overline{U'U'} .$$

Commonly, the Reynolds-stress tensor is reformulated from the Boussinesq hypothesis, and a turbulence model brings closure to the system of equations.

Large-Eddy Simulation

The basis of LES is a high-pass scale (low-pass frequency) filter operator of the form

$$\tilde{\phi}(P, t) = \int_D \phi(P', t) G(P - P', \tilde{\Delta}) dP' , \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{\phi}$ denotes the filtering of the flow variable ϕ , G is a convolution filter, $\tilde{\Delta}$ is the filter width, and D is the entire domain (Piomelli, 2021). Imposing Eq. 8 on the flow variables of Eq. 5 yields the filtered Navier-Stokes equations

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \cdot \tilde{U} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{U} + \nabla \cdot (\tilde{U}\tilde{U}) &= \nu \nabla^2 \tilde{U} - \nabla \cdot \frac{\tilde{p}}{\rho} + g - \nabla \cdot (\tilde{U}\tilde{U} - \tilde{U}\tilde{U}) .\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

Analogously to the Reynolds-stress tensor in the URANS equations in Eq. 7, a residual stress term

arises after filtering, i.e.,

$$\overline{\sigma_{SGS}} = \overline{UU} - \tilde{U}\tilde{U},$$

which is commonly referred to as the subgrid-scale (SGS) stress tensor. As with $\overline{\sigma_t}$, $\overline{\sigma_{SGS}}$ is usually reformulated by the Boussinesq hypothesis and a SGS turbulence model is adopted to bring closure to the system.

Detached-Eddy Simulation

The original DES method of Spalart et al. (1997) substitutes the wall distance d_w as the length scale of the Spalart-Allmaras (S-A) turbulence model with the DES length scale

$$l_{DES-S-A} = \min(d_w, C_{DES}\Delta), \quad (10)$$

where Δ is the local cell size and C_{DES} a calibration constant. This reformulation effectively turns the S-A model into a SGS turbulence model of Smagorinsky-like type for $d_w \gg \Delta$, meaning that the turbulent viscosity scales with the magnitude of the local strain rate and the cell size squared (Strelets, 2001). Strelets (2001) formulated and calibrated a DES version of the popular k - ω -SST turbulence model (Menter and Esch, 2001) from its length scale

$$l_{M-SST} = \sqrt{k}/(\beta^*\omega)$$

with k being the turbulence kinetic energy, β^* a model constant, and ω the turbulence specific dissipation rate. In Strelets (2001), this length scale was substituted with $l_{DES-M-SST} = \min(l_{M-SST}, C_{DES}\Delta)$ in the dissipative term of the k -transport equation, securing Smagorinsky-like behavior at turbulence equilibrium. Furthermore, C_{DES} in the SGS formulation of the k - ω -SST model was calibrated from decaying homogeneous isotropic turbulence tests – similar assumptions used for derivation of the corresponding coefficient in the Smagorinsky model, see Lilly (1966).

TEST SET-UP

All simulations employed the k - ω -SST DES formulation (as per Strelets, 2001) in the open-source framework OpenFOAM-v2106 (OpenCFD, 2023; Weller et al, 1998). OpenFOAM is based on a cell-centred 2nd order finite volume method that supports unstructured polyhedral cells. In the present work the incompressible solver pisoFOAM, based on the PISO algorithm for pressure-velocity coupling, was used. In this work pisoFOAM utilizes implicitly filtered LES, referring to an actual convolution filter kernel never being imposed, but rather the filtering being implicitly defined from the available resolution, numerical truncation errors, and SGS model (Lampitella, 2014).

All spatial discretization schemes are second order accurate. Second-order central differences were chosen for diffusion and for the convection of momentum in LES-mode, as well as for gradient and Laplacian terms. Upwind second-order differences were chosen for the convection of momentum in RANS-mode and for the convection of k and ω . The time-stepping was carried out by a stabilized second-order Crank-Nicolson scheme.

A nominally two-dimensional plate of height h , span $4h$, and thickness $0.02h$ was oriented normally to a constant streamwise velocity u_0 . The corresponding Re was $1.5e5$. The relative curvature radius

of the corners was varied as $r/h \in [0.0, 0.5, 1.0]\%$, see Fig. 1. The domain dimensions and boundary conditions (BCs) are outlined in Fig. 3. Velocity U is given as Dirichlet and Neumann type BCs at the inlet and outlet, respectively, and vice versa with the pressure p , see Fig. 3. The domain sizes and BCs were chosen to match Tian et al. (2014), where the spanwise dimension of $4h$ was chosen to accommodate multiple spanwise vortical rib structures.

Fig. 3: Conceptual setup of numerical tests. Please note that origin of the global coordinate system is located at the center of the plate.

The OpenFOAM mesh tools blockMesh and refineMesh were used to generate the meshes. The meshes were predominantly hexahedral (98%) while the remainder was of polyhedral type used in intersections between refinement regions. 25 inflation layers were included around the plate with a first cell layer thickness corresponding to $y^+ < 1$ throughout all simulations. The mesh was asymmetrical about the y -axis as higher resolutions and more delicate refinement strategies were applied in the focus region, where the (near) wake transpires, relative to the Euler region in accordance with the DES mesh guidelines in Spalart and Streett (2001). See Fig. 4. A uniform cell spacing was used in z as also employed in Tian et al. (2014) and Díaz-Ojeda et al. (2019). A constant time step was invoked in all simulations.

Fig. 4: View of the far- (a) and near-field mesh (b) in the xy -plane for Case 7 in Table 2.

SOLUTION VERIFICATION

Solution verification is carried out by Richardson Extrapolation (RE) and the Grid Convergence Index (GCI) to estimate numerical uncertainties. The procedure follows that of Eça et al. (2011). The verification variable is chosen as the time-averaged drag coefficient, $\langle C_D \rangle_t$. For the present paper, the grid refinement ratio h_i/h_1 is based on the number of cells in the xy -plane, corresponding to

$$h_i/h_1 = (N_{cells,1}/N_{cells,i})^{1/2},$$

where N_{cells} is the total number of cells and subscript i is the grid index which equals 1 for the highest resolution. Numerical uncertainty is widely accepted to be composed of discretization errors, iterative errors, and round-off errors (Eça et al., 2011). Round-off errors are negligible with the use of double precision and iterative errors are closely linked to the time step for unsteady simulations. Sensitivity to the temporal and spanwise resolutions are assessed more loosely than of the xy spatial resolution, and only few coarser temporal and spanwise resolutions have been considered, see Table 2.

Table 2: Investigated spatial and temporal resolutions. N_z denotes the number of cells in the spanwise direction.

Case	h_i/h_1 [-]	N_{cells} [1e6 cells]	N_z [cells]	$\Delta t u_0/h$ [-]	$\langle C_D \rangle_t$ [-]	Δ_{rel} [%]	$U_{\langle C_D \rangle_t}$ [%]
1	1.00	10.3	48	6e-4	2.28	0.0	2.7
2	1.29	6.0	48	6e-4	2.28	0.2	3.7
3	1.49	4.5	48	6e-4	2.26	0.6	4.6
4	1.66	3.6	48	6e-4	2.23	2.1	5.4
5	2.08	2.3	48	6e-4	2.23	2.1	7.8
6	2.58	1.5	48	6e-4	2.10	8.0	11.3
7	3.16	1.0	48	6e-4	2.05	9.9	16.4
8	-	4.5	48	1.2e-3	2.22	1.8	-
9	-	4.5	48	2.4e-3	2.26	0.0	-
10	-	4.5	48	4.8e-3	2.25	0.4	-
11	-	2.3	24	6e-4	2.19	3.1	-
12	-	1.1	12	6e-4	4.06	82.1	-

Initial conditions were mapped from a preliminary DES solution executed with a high temporal resolution ($\Delta t u_0/h < 6e-5$), a moderate spatial resolution ($N_{cells} = 4.5e6$ cells), and a duration of $30h/u_0$. After mapping, the flow re-developed for $70h/u_0$ (following Tian et al., 2014) before statistical averaging was carried out for a duration of $245h/u_0$.

The variation of temporal and spanwise resolutions suggests that the results are rather insensitive to the choice of resolution for $\Delta t u_0/h \leq 1.2e-3$ and $N_z \geq 24$, which yielded relative deviations, Δ_{rel} , of 1.8% and 3.1% to the reference Case 3. Numerical uncertainty is thus estimated from the discretization errors from the spatial resolution in the xy -plane. Solution verification is only carried out for the plate geometry with $r/h = 1.0\%$. The estimated convergence of $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ with the spatial resolution in the xy -plane can be seen in Fig. 5, where least square fits to power functions of the form $\alpha(h_i/h_1)^{\gamma_0} + \beta$ are imposed to estimate the rate of convergence (γ_0). RE is applied to the least square fits to calculate the numerical uncertainty $U_{\langle C_D \rangle_t}$ which is the expanded uncertainty at a 95% confidence level (Roache, 2009), see Table 2. The Case 1-3 meshes all have less than 5% numerical uncertainty and can be judged as acceptable resolutions.

Fig. 5: Estimated convergence of $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ from spatial resolution in the xy -plane. γ_o denotes the convergence rate.

A special trait of using SRS rather than SMS is that the modelling error (from turbulence) diminishes with the discretization error. This is an effect of the governing equations of DES (in LES mode) being tied directly to the local cell sizes. More accurate turbulence descriptions in the form of extended ranges of resolved scales are thus obtained for higher resolutions using DES. This effect is visualized from isosurfaces by the Q -criterion for $Q = 0.01$ with Cases 5, 3, 2, and 1 in Fig. 6. For higher resolutions (lower case numbers) the departure region is extended further downstream improving the accuracy of the “boundary condition” to the focus region (near-wake).

RESULTS

Global flow values are calculated for the three investigated corner curvatures, see Table 3. The Case 1 grid is adopted for the simulations on smaller corner curvatures. The far-field mesh is maintained while the near-field mesh is changed to accommodate the changes in plate geometry. Simulations are initiated in the same way as in the solution verification, meaning that a DES solution with $r/h = 1.0\%$ is mapped after which the flow is allowed to redevelop for $70h/u_0$ before statistical averaging is carried out for a duration of $245h/u_0$. The drag coefficient time series are shown in Fig. 7. The pressure coefficient on the plate is calculated by $C_p = 2(p - p_0)/(\rho u_0^2)$ where p_0 is the reference pressure taken as the inlet pressure at $y = 0$. The time- and spanwise averaged pressure coefficient distribution is shown in Fig. 8. The time- and spanwise averaged x -component of the velocity vector at $y = 0$ is shown in Fig. 9 (used for calculation of the recirculation length). The Strouhal numbers are in Table 3 given from the peak frequency in the lift power spectrum presented in Fig. 10.

Table 3: Global flow values for the investigated corner curvatures.

r/h [%]	$\langle C_D \rangle_t$ [-]	L_C [-]	S_t [-]
1.0	2.28	2.10	0.157
0.5	2.26	2.18	0.155
0.0	2.42	1.98	0.155

Fig. 6: Effect of mesh resolution on the wake illustrated by Q -isosurface ($Q = 0.01$) for Cases 1-3 and 5. Coloring by the magnitude of the velocity vector U .

Fig. 7: Time series of the drag coefficient.

Fig. 8: Time- and spanwise averaged pressure coefficient distribution.

Fig. 9: Time- and spanwise averaged x -component of velocity at $y = 0$.

Fig. 10: Power spectral density (PSD) of the lift force.

To further estimate the effect of the corner curvatures on the shape of the wake regions the isosurface of the time-averaged velocity magnitude for $|\langle U \rangle_t|/u_0 = 2/3$ is calculated, see Fig. 11.

Fig. 11: Isosurface of time-averaged velocity magnitude, $|\langle U \rangle_t|/u_0 = 2/3$, for different corner curvatures.

In Fig. 12, $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ from the present work are presented with that of literature (as previously presented in Fig. 5). The result for $r/h = 1.0\%$ is included with an error bar indicating a double-sided 95% confidence interval (CI) from the numerical uncertainty.

Fig. 12: Present results with 95% CI together with results from literature.

DISCUSSION

From Table 3 and Fig. 12, a monotonic trend of $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ with r/h was not disclosed over the investigated range. The difference between $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ at $r/h = 1.0\%$ and 0.5% is less than the numerical uncertainty at $r/h = 1.0\%$ with a 95% confidence level. However, a significant increase of $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ was found between $r/h = 1.0\%$ (semicylindrical edges) and $r/h = 0.0\%$ (sharp corners). The latter follows the tendency of DNV (2017) and Tian et al. (2014). For $r/h = 1.0\%$ and 0.0% , $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ and L_C are over- and underestimated, respectively, relative to the literature for $t/h \ll 1$ (flat plates). For $r/h = 0.5\%$, $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ and L_C are slightly under- and overestimated, respectively, but in close agreement with those of Tian et al. (2014), i.e., less than 2.5% deviation. $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ and L_C are thus not consistently either over- or underestimated relative to the literature for the tested range of r/h .

Assuming equal error bars on $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ for $r/h = 0.5\%$ and 0.0% as for 1.0% , the correlation of $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ and r/h in the investigated range cannot be rejected to be equal that of Tian et al. (2014) and DNV (2017). Assuming (somewhat crudely) equal error bars on $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ for all numerical results in Fig. 12, the present DES results is only validated against LES with the Smagorinsky SGS model from Tian et al. (2014) and Díaz-Ojeda et al. (2018) given the same corner curvatures. The relative deviations are 1.8-3.5%, which is commonly accepted as minor deviations in a CFD context. The present DES $k-\omega$ -SST SGS model will in turbulence equilibrium behave Smagorinsky-like and hence similar to the LES in Tian et al. (2014) and Díaz-Ojeda et al. (2018) given comparable resolutions (and numerics). Similar domains and resolutions have been applied in the convergence analysis of Tian et al. (2014), and DES does not seem to improve the accuracy-cost trade-off in the considered application significantly over LES. A point for future investigation is to run LES on the exact same grids as applied in the present work.

As expected, the frequency of vortex shedding (governing the frequency of lift forces) is dominant around a single frequency, see Fig. 10. The Strouhal number is basically invariant with r/h from the present results (Table 3 and Fig. 10) with less than 1% deviation for the tested r/h ratios, and less than 2% deviation relative to Tian et al. (2014) and Hemmati et al. (2018).

C_D varies drastically over time, up to 60% between global minima and maxima, and the temporal evolution suggest distinct modes of the shedding process, see Fig. 7. High and low intensity shedding regimes behind nominally 2-D flat plates are reported in the literature by, e.g., Najjar and Balachandar (1998) and Hemmati et al. (2016), which concluded that global flow values vary notably between the different shedding regimes. Hence, statistical averaging ought only to be carried out for time series containing several high and low regime cycles.

Knowing $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ for the different plate geometries the tendencies are as expected with the pressure coefficient distributions and the recirculation length behind the plate. Base pressure distributions are close to constant over the plate width, y , see Fig. 8. The base pressures vary with r/h and scale with the relative differences of $\langle C_D \rangle_t$, while the pressure distributions on the upstream face only vary close to the edges. Higher base pressures and $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ are associated with lower recirculation lengths, see Fig. 9. The isosurfaces of $|\langle U \rangle_t|/u_0 = 2/3$ can be used for visualization of the shape of the time-averaged wake, see Fig. 11. From this, the immediate curvatures of the respective wakes are as expected; steeper slopes and slight, positive offsets in y for lower r/h directly due to the different geometrical features. Further downstream, the isosurfaces with the steeper immediate slopes are expected to curve relatively more as seen for $r/h = 1.0\%$ and 0.0% causing lower recirculation lengths for higher r/h and ultimately higher $\langle C_D \rangle_t$. However, the isosurface for $r/h = 0.5\%$ curves the least and in turn has the highest recirculation length. The relative positioning of the isosurfaces follows the attained global flow values but opposes the expected physics which may be ascribed to too small variations of $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ in (part) of the tested r/h range relative to the numerical uncertainties.

CONCLUSIONS

Global flow quantities in the normal flow past flat plates have been calculated with DES coupled with the $k-\omega$ -SST turbulence model. The corner curvature of the plate has been varied in $r/h = [0.0, 0.5, 1.0]\%$. For $r/h = 1.0\%$, solution verification was carried out and numerical uncertainty was quantified. The expanded uncertainty was estimated as 2.7% of the time-averaged drag coefficient at the 95% confidence level. An insignificant increase in $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ was found by varying $r/h = 1.0\%$ to 0.5% , while a significant increase was found for $r/h = 1.0\%$ (semicylindrical edges) to 0.0% (sharp corners) at the 95% confidence level. The latter had an increase of both $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ and L_C of about 6%. S_t remained close to invariant with r/h . For identical corner curvatures $\langle C_D \rangle_t$ deviated maximally 3.5% between the present DES and LES with the Smagorinsky SGS model from papers with comparable model setups – suggesting little influence of the turbulence description between the two models on integral values for the considered application.

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